

TEACHER-STUDENT SYSTEM ON THE BASIS OF THE CURRENT EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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It is known that the center of social processes of the XXI century is man, his thinking and intellectual potential. In particular, the issue of forming harmonious and active youth, which has become a requirement of the time, imposes a great responsibility on educators. A comprehensive approach to the concepts of personal maturity, upbringing and culture, and its perception as an integral part of spirituality, has become one of the most pressing issues today. First of all, the effectiveness of reforms in other spheres of our life is inextricably linked with the revival of the people's spirituality, the extensive study of our rich historical heritage, the preservation of our traditions, the development of culture and art, science and education.

Extensive reforms in the field of education, in particular, the update of the

ABSTRACT

This article describes the teacher-student relationship in the educational process, their basic rules of law, basic rights, obligations and, of course, the duties of teacher and student. In addition, special emphasis was placed on the importance of teacher-student relations not only in education but also in upbringing.

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" have identified important strategic directions. On the basis of these strategic directions, a lot of work is being done to further improve the quality of training, to bring up a person who is professionally competitive, spiritually mature, loyal to national values and traditions, full of patriotism. One of them is the revival of the Master - Disciple tradition. The traditions of teacher and student also exist in foreign countries. In particular, the Tutor system in the United Kingdom, the Teacher-Student system in Belgium, and the Sponsorship system in Israel play an important role in ensuring the relevance of the Anglo-Saxon school in the world. In the history of our people, the "Master-Disciple" system has survived for many centuries. Just as each system has its own set of rules and regulations, over the

centuries the system " Master-Disciple " has formed and improved its rules. In modern educational system, this regulation reveals one by one the rules and responsibilities of the "teacher-student" system.

Basic rules:

The teacher-student system will be introduced in parallel with the curatorial system in higher education. The main purpose of the introduction of the "teacher-student" system is to harmonize vocational education and training and ensure its effectiveness.

At the beginning of the academic year (September) in higher education institutions, according to the "Master - Disciple" charter, students are given the time and opportunity to choose teachers for themselves and for teachers to choose students. There will also be an explanatory work on the essence of the "Teacher-Student" system among students of faculties and departments of higher education institutions.

The dean of the faculty will be notified in writing about the selected teachers and students. Applications will be reviewed by the department and the dean of the faculty, and the number and composition of students will be determined for each faculty member. The number of students assigned to each teacher is determined by the structural characteristics of the department and faculty.

The dean of the faculty summarizes the proposals received from students and teachers and discusses them with the departments and submits a notice to the rector for approval. The number of students to be attached to each "Teacher"

(based on the list) is approved by order of the rector.

The competition, conducted by a student or faculty member, is formalized with the consent of both parties (faculty and student). After getting to know each other, the teacher and the student work together to develop a plan for the school year. The plan should cover such aspects of life as professional training, mastering, attendance, research work, living conditions, economic status, and should focus on the comprehensive formation of the student as a professional and an individual.

The teacher is subordinate to the deans of the faculties where the students are studying and directly to the vice-rectors for educational and spiritual-educational work and relies on their instructions. In his work, the teacher is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Presidential Decrees, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, orders of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, the Charter of the Higher Education Institution, internal regulations and the "Teacher and Student" works. Each Higher Education Institution's Educational and Methodological Council will have permanent Councils to promote the best practices of teachers. It is recommended that each higher education institution have a staff of sociologists and psychologists who serve the teacher-student system.

Duties, responsibilities and rights of the teacher

1. The teacher becomes a leading specialist in his field, instilling in his students a sense of love and devotion to the Fatherland, respect for universal and national values, humanity and diligence, and a correct

understanding of the changes taking place in our society and provides practical and methodological assistance in achieving.

2. Regularly studies and analyzes the student's mastery of subjects, research, worldview and interests in the chosen specialty, and projects the organization of the educational process with the student. Introduces and assists students in their duties and rights as a student, the requirements for a future professional, the internal procedures of the higher education institution and the obligations arising from the contracts concluded with the higher education institution.

3. Helps students choose a research topic by exploring their abilities, interests, and intellectual potential.

4. Provides necessary advice to students in determining research topics. Conducts regular research on a topic of his / her choice during his / her university studies.

5. Prepares students for scientific activities, organizes their independent research activities.

6. Assists students in the systematic planning of research activities, setting goals and objectives, research methods, and working with information sources, data collection, analysis and generalization.

7. Develops students' research skills.

8. Scientific and creative organization of scientific activity in students, clear planning of work, systematic design, anticipation of problems that may occur during the activity and independent search for ways to overcome them, to draw the right conclusions, forms qualities such as ensuring labor productivity.

9. In the organization of independent research focuses on the correct orientation

of the work of students on scientific and practical sources.

10. Conducts research in collaboration with students, works on creating an experimental basis.

11. Conducts research in fundamental and innovative areas with students.

12. Participates in international and national grant competitions, exhibitions with active involvement of students in research work. Develops in students the skills of organizing professional activities on a scientific basis, participation in the integration of science and industry, innovative organization of labor.

13. Assists in the development of research results at the level of graduate and master's dissertations.

14. Regularly acquaints students with the life, history, traditions of the institution of higher education, the main directions of research activities of faculties and departments, the activities of public organizations and monitors their independent study.

15. Based on the psychological characteristics of each student, teachers help their students to develop as a self-governing person united around a common goal of becoming a qualified professional, a mature person and a dedicated patriot. The university and the faculty involve their students in public affairs.

16. Helps students to become morally and ethically mature.

17. Organizes roundtables, excursions and other activities with students on the tasks of future professionals.

18. Helps students to develop a positive attitude to world events, changes in our country, the life of the university and

faculty, to give them an independent opinion on these issues.

19. Promotes a healthy lifestyle, organizes the participation of students in various scientific, technical, creative and artistic circles, sports sections and competitions.

20. Supervises students' regular attendance, daily and sessional learning.

21. Provides recommendations to encourage outstanding and active students, recommends state scholarships, warns students who are lagging behind in mastering, organizes consultations for them with the help of teachers of the department.

22. Teacher is responsible for students who violate internal regulations, act contrary to the rules of morality and ethics, do not pay enough attention to the lessons of the teacher, and together with the structures of the higher education institution teacher must way out of such complex situations

24. Considers and is responsible for providing personal assistance to students in the learning process and in domestic matters, as well as in providing spiritual and material support.

25. Participates in meetings of universities and faculties on the issue of teachers and students, exchanges views on the experience of the educational process, makes suggestions on these issues.

26. The department solves the issues of attendance of students in the disciplines, obtaining information on the results of rating control and tests, as well as consultations with students who are lagging behind in mastering.

27. Participates in the internship of students and the distribution of jobs.

28. It is responsible for both professional and social development of students during and after their studies in higher education.

Rights

- to ask and make suggestions to the heads of departments, deans of faculties, rectors and public organizations to improve the educational process, educational and research work, to inform the university and faculty management about the wishes and needs of students;
- to get acquainted with and study the documents of his students kept in the dean's office;
- to protect the rights of students in education and training, if necessary, to assist them in this matter;
- make suggestions on financial aid to the student;
- to receive additional payment for full and exemplary performance of teaching duties on the recommendation of the deans;
- in case of non-fulfillment of the student's obligations, the teacher submits a written information to the dean of the faculty and demands that the dean of the faculty study and take appropriate action;
- during the academic year, the teacher is allowed to change the student by the decision of the rector, if there are objective reasons;
- the university has the right to make proposals to the administration of the faculty, public organizations to take administrative action against students who are lagging behind in encouraging or mastering exemplary students.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with all sectors, is carrying out large-scale reforms in the education system. The results of these changes are inextricably linked with the fact that our country

occupies a worthy place among the developed countries, first of all, with the development of science and education. To further increase the effectiveness of ongoing reforms, to create conditions for the comprehensive development of the state and society, to modernize the country and liberalize all living conditions, to provide modern education to students methods in education are being developed.

At the same time, it is difficult to increase the effectiveness of education, to ensure that students fully master the knowledge, skills and competencies set by state educational standards, to ensure independent learning, to master the gifted, talented and individual subjects. One of the urgent tasks is to take an individual approach to students, to develop the best qualities of students, to pay serious attention to the organization of lessons,

identifying the interests, needs, abilities, intellectual and personal qualities of young people. It should be noted that today some work is being done to update and improve the content of education, increase the effectiveness of teaching and professionalism of teachers, the dissemination of best practices.

No matter how much the education system has changed or modernized, education based on the teacher-student relationship has always played an important role. Such relations, of course, are based on specific laws and regulations. In this article the regulation of the teacher-student relationship (based on the system of higher education) and, of course, in this relationship, the tasks, duties and rights of each participant and even each element are defined.

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